

Cu-BTC functional microdevices as smart tools for capture and preconcentration of nerve agents

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18 **KEYWORDS:** microfabrication, copper modified glass substrates, threshold current density,
19 integration of metal organic framework films, co-adsorbed water vapor, nerve agents capture

20

21 **ABSTRACT:** Cu-based Metal Organic Frameworks (MOF) microdevices are applied in
22 sampling and preconcentration of nerve agents (NAs) diluted in gaseous streams. An *in-situ*
23 electrochemical assisted synthesis of Cu-BTC thick film is carried out to functionalize a Cu
24 modified glass substrate. This simple, rapid, reproducible and easy to integrate MOF synthesis
25 approach, enables the microfabrication of functional micropreconcentrators with large BET
26 surface area (above 2000 cm²) and active pore volume (above 90 nanoliters) for the efficient
27 adsorption of nerve agent molecules along the microfluidic channel 2.5 cm in length. Equilibrium
28 adsorption capacity of the bulk material has been characterized through thermogravimetric
29 analysis after exposure to controlled atmospheres of a sarin gas surrogate, dimethyl
30 methylphosphonate (DMMP), in both dry and humid conditions (30% RH at 293 K).
31 Breakthrough tests at ppm level (162 mg/m³) reveal equilibrium adsorption capacities up to 691
32 mg/g. The preconcentration performance of such μ -devices when dealing with highly diluted
33 surrogate atmosphere, i.e. 520 ppbV (2.6 mg/m³) at 298 K, leads to preconcentration coefficients
34 up to 171 for sample volume up to 600 STP cm³. We demonstrate the potentialities of Cu-BTC
35 micropreconcentrators as smart first responder tools for “on field” detection of nerve agents in
36 gas phase at relevant conditions.

37

38 INTRODUCTION

39 Vulnerability of critical indoor infrastructures to intentional nerve agents release poses a
40 significant point of concern for authorities responsible for incident preparedness and prevention.
41 Such chemical compounds are odorless, colorless, highly persistent, volatile and lethal even at
42 low concentration.¹ Particularly, the organophosphonates-based nerve agents (NAs), where the
43 well-known sarin and soman gases belong to, have been used against civilian population in
44 shocking terrorist attacks. Infamously known are the terrorist attack in the subway of Tokyo in
45 1991 and the recent ones against civilians in Syria.² A few studies are available for sarin vapor
46 exposures on human volunteers in order to directly derive acute exposure guideline levels.
47 Results indicate that the threshold for miosis and other minimal toxic effects falls in the range of
48 $0.05 - 0.5 \text{ mg/m}^3$ ($9 - 87 \text{ ppbV}$) for 30 - 10 min exposures, respectively.³

49 Due to the potential threat that NAs constitute against the population, many efforts have been
50 dedicated to its early detection. To improve the limit of detection of the available equipment, a
51 common solution is to implement a trapping-preconcentration unit upstream the detector. This
52 approach has been successfully applied in many fields where the identification of compounds at
53 very low concentration (sub ppmV) is required; such as workplace health and safety⁴ or for non-
54 invasive, diagnostic tools based on the detection of exhaled volatile biomarkers⁵. Enrichment
55 factors up to 300 have been reported for aromatic VOCs using carbon nanotubes-based μ -
56 preconcentrators for 100 ppbV feed concentration and sample volume up to 400 STP cm^3 .⁶

57 MOFs are hybrid materials composed of coordinatively linked metal ions or clusters via
58 organic ligands to form porous crystalline frameworks with proven microporosity. Compared to
59 microporous zeolites or mesoporous silica, MOFs exhibit higher chemical versatility.
60 Remarkable adsorption capacities have been reported towards organophosphonate compounds.

61 The isoreticular IRMOF-1 $Zn_4O(dmcapz)_3$, dmcapz stands for 4-carboxy-3,5-
62 dimethylpyrazolate, exhibits an adsorption capacity up to 950 mg DMMP/g IRMOF-1 for
63 saturated atmosphere of dimethyl methylphosphonate (DMMP) at 50 °C ⁷; as well as mild
64 adsorption heat values ($-\Delta H_{ads} = 44.8$ kJ/mol for diisopropylfluorophosphate (DIFP) at
65 temperatures ranging from 383 to 513 K ⁸). Newly developed Zr-based MOFs, such as NU-1000,
66 UiO-66 or MOF-808, have attracted interest in NAs decontamination not only due to their
67 sorption properties (713 mgDMMP/gNU-1000 and 152 mgDMMP/gUiO-66 for 507 mg/m³
68 DMMP at 298K ⁹) but also due to their catalytic properties towards organophosphorus
69 degradation by hydrolysis.¹⁰

70 Cu-based MOFs, such as Cu-BTC (HKUST-1), have also been widely reported as adequate
71 adsorbents for organophosphorous vapors due the high affinity that those compounds exhibit
72 towards Cu clusters and the stability of the resulting metal complexes. Fourier-transformation
73 infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy analysis on surface acoustic wave type sensors functionalized via
74 self-assembled monolayer with $-(CO_2)_2Cu$ as terminal group and exposed to diisopropyl
75 methylphosphonate (DIMP) in gas phase reveal the formation of Cu–DIMP complexes (P=O-
76 Cu). ¹¹ The affinity of organophosphorous compounds to copper ions still prevails in HKUST-1
77 as demonstrated by the experimentally measured adsorption heat value for
78 diisopropylfluorophosphate (DIFP), $-\Delta H_{ads} = 48.4$ kJ/mol, which is higher than that observed for
79 commercial Carboxen, $-\Delta H_{ads} = 38.3$ kJ/mol.¹² Finally, theoretical computational models¹³ using
80 density functional theory (DFT) point out that the most favorable MOFs, among the 1544 MOFs
81 tested, for Sarin gas adsorption are those with pore sizes in the range of 6-8 Å. Smaller pores
82 cannot accommodate Sarin molecules and on larger pores the molecular interactions with the
83 framework become weaker. Accordingly, Cu-BTC emerges as potential adsorbent for

84 organophosphonates compounds thanks to its pore size distribution¹⁴ and the chemical affinity of
85 the Cu nodes. Thus, well-intergrowth layers of Cu-BTC on microfluidic devices are herein
86 explored to capture and preconcentrate DMMP, a Sarin surrogate, from highly diluted gas
87 streams.

88 The synthesis of MOF films has been particularly of interest in the field of chemical sensors¹⁵
89 and gas membranes for selective separations¹⁶. Novel approaches such as microfluidic pen
90 lithography¹⁷ or inkjet printing technology are gaining importance due to their potential for large
91 scale manufacturing of functional microdevices. Recently, UiO-66 has been synthesized in situ
92 by inkjet printing on resonant Si microcantilevers with piezoresistive detection, which have been
93 applied to DMMP sensing with theoretical limit of detection down to 0.025 mg/m³ (5 ppbV).¹⁸

94 In this work, in situ electrochemical growth of Cu-BTC, a well-known MOF material that has
95 been extensively investigated both experimentally and theoretically, on a glass modified
96 substrate is carried out to functionalize μ -preconcentrators for NAs^{19,20} in order to demonstrate
97 the potentialities for capture and preconcentration applications. The micropatterned Cu electrode
98 is exposed to the electrolyte solution and used as metal source for the in situ electrochemical
99 synthesis of Cu-BTC films following a similar approach to our previous publications²¹. The work
100 is divided in two parts. The first part is devoted to study the influence of the current density and
101 number of electrosynthesis cycles on the heterogeneous MOF crystallization rate, crystal
102 morphology and surface coverage of the glass substrate. Special attention is paid to the nature of
103 the Cu adhesion promoters (Au-Cr vs. Ti). As a result, an optimum potentiometric procedure is
104 defined for the fabrication of functional microdevices based on Cu-BTC films. The second part
105 is focused on the adsorption performance of the functional μ -preconcentrators towards DMMP.
106 Equilibrium uptake values, dynamic adsorption properties from breakthrough tests at ppmV level

107 and preconcentration coefficients are evaluated and compared with published data. Furthermore,
108 the molecular interactions of DMMP with Cu-BTC and Cu/Cu₂O surfaces in dry and humid
109 conditions are computationally studied to gain insight into the experimental results. Thus, this
110 work constitutes one of the still very scarce reports on MOF based functional microdevices. To
111 the best of our knowledge, continuous Cu-BTC films and Si based microfluidic devices are
112 combined for the first time to be employed efficiently in sampling and preconcentration
113 applications of toxic compounds.

114 **EXPERIMENTAL SECTION**

115 **μ-preconcentrator fabrication**

116 The μ-preconcentrator device is composed of two parts: 1) a microfluidic channel on a Si
117 substrate and 2) a glass substrate where the adsorbent is synthesized. The microfluidic channel,
118 2.5cm length and 20 μm depth, on un-doped <100>-oriented, polycrystalline 500 ± 20 μm Si
119 wafer is fabricated as previously described.²² Channel depth has been confirmed by profilometry.
120 Each 4-inch Si wafer contains 8 different microdevices substrates, which are diced apart after the
121 process is finished (see Section 1 of the Supporting Information).

122 The electrochemical synthesis of the Cu-BTC was performed on the micropatterned copper on
123 the Borofloat substrate as electrodes (Sigert Wafer, 500 ± 20 μm thickness, surface roughness <
124 1.2 nm). In particular, two different Cu modified glass substrates have been investigated (Figure
125 1) to analyze the influence of the metal adhesion layer: i) 200 nm of Cu over an adhesion layer of
126 10 nm Cr and 50 nm Au denoted as Cu-Cr/Au substrate (0.52 cm² metallized surface) and ii) 500
127 nm Cu over an adhesion layer of 40 nm Ti denoted as Cu-Ti substrate (0.69 cm² metallized
128 surface). The finished Borofloat wafer is also diced in 8 different substrates and processed
129 individually.

130 After the Cu-BTC MOF synthesis, the Borofloat substrate is bonded to its Si counterpart by
 131 anodic bonding and fluidic ports were inserted to connect to transfer lines. Computer modelling
 132 in COMSOL Multiphysics of the microfluidic device was performed in advance to ensure
 133 hydraulic compliance with the anodic bonding sealing. Thus, theoretical ΔP value of 244 mbar
 134 for 10 STP cm^3/min was calculated. It is noteworthy to underline that cavity depths varying from
 135 20 μm to 120 μm were scrutinized by CFD simulations. In addition, preliminary breakthrough
 136 tests, not shown here, revealed the existence of an optimal trade-off at 20 μm channel depth
 137 which ensures efficient sorbate-sorbent contact at affordable pressure drop values for the
 138 working conditions herein studied (flow rate and DMMP concentration).

139
 140 **Figure 1.** Main steps of the microdevice fabrication. a) Borofloat substrate. b) Cu based
 141 deposition on Borofloat substrates (used as reference: Cu - Cr/Au and Cu - Ti substrates. c)
 142 electrochemical synthesis of the Cu-BTC on Borofloat substrate. d) anodic bonding with Si
 143 counterpart.

144 **Synthesis and characterization of Cu-BTC films on Borofloat substrates**

145 The electrosynthesis of Cu-BTC was carried out as previously reported (see Section 2 of the
146 Supporting Information).²¹ Using an Autolab potentiostat PGSTAT302N, cyclic pulses of
147 different current (ranging from 1 to 15 mA) were applied between the Cu modified glass
148 substrate used as working electrode and the counter-electrode. In this work, different
149 electrosynthesis parameters were explored (Table 1) in order to maximize heterogeneous Cu-
150 BTC crystallization, surface coverage and homogeneity. Very preliminary results, not shown
151 here, performed with the same electrochemical cell revealed the existence of a minimum current
152 density value, *i.e.* 1.5 mA/cm², for heterogeneous synthesis on Cu-Cr/Au modified glass
153 substrates. Above this current density, an adequate concentration of Cu²⁺ ions, as net mass
154 balance resulting from the generation term by Cu electrode oxidation and the consumption term
155 by Cu-BTC formation, remains in the electrolyte solution for the successful nucleation and
156 growth on the working electrode. Current duty cycle, *i.e.* on/off switching of applied current, was
157 kept constant through all of the experiments ($t_{\text{cycle}} = 20$ s, duty cycle = 0.75, *i.e.* $t_{\text{on}} = 15$ s, $t_{\text{off}} =$
158 5s).

159 Cu-BTC coatings were firstly characterized by optical inspection supported by the turquoise
160 (water coordinated state) color that Cu-BTC exhibits. SEM-EDX analyses (INSPECT-F50) were
161 performed to determine the composition and morphology of the films. Purity and crystallinity of
162 the Cu-BTC coatings were evaluated by surface X-ray diffraction (Bruker D8 Advance High
163 Resolution Diffractometer) and XPS (Kratos Axis X-ray spectrometer).

164

165 **Table 1.** Electrosynthesis conditions studied in this work.

<i>Substrate</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>I_{synthesis}</i>	<i>J_{synthesis} (mA/cm²)</i>	<i>N_{cycles}</i>
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		<i>(mA)</i>		
Cu-Cr/Au	#1_12	1.0	1.6	12
	#2_12			12
	#2_15	9.0	17.3	15
	#2_20			20
	#3_12	15.0	28.8	12
Cu-Ti	#4_15*	6.0	8.7	15
	#5_7			7
	#5_15	12.0	17.4	15

166 * Conditions selected for the fabrication and testing of the functional microdevices studied in
167 this work.

168 **Adsorption properties of Cu-BTC**

169 The textural properties of Cu-BTC films were assessed from Ar physisorption analysis, carried
170 out on commercial Cu-BTC in powder form, Basolite C300, purchased from Sigma Aldrich. The
171 as received bulk material was also used to quantify the adsorption properties towards DMMP
172 when exposed to 3748 mg/m³ of DMMP at 293 K (in dry air and at 30 % RH at 293K). Similar
173 experiments were performed on previously activated samples (degassed overnight in an oven at
174 423 K and atmospheric pressure) to analyze the influence of water content on DMMP adsorption
175 properties. An aliquot of the exposed MOF as well as of the activated material were taken and
176 analyzed by thermogravimetry on a TA Instruments TGA-Q5000 (using N₂ up to 873 K at 10
177 K/min as heating rate). Quantification was performed using CuO as basis of calculation.

178 Theoretical adsorption isotherms have been calculated by combination of Monte Carlo (MC)
179 simulations, in particular, by using the Metropolis–Hastings algorithm and molecular dynamics
180 calculations based on UFF²³ as a force field.

181 Dynamic and equilibrium adsorption properties of the functional Cu-BTC μ preconcentrators as
182 well as uncoated counterparts, with and without micropatterned Cu electrode, have been
183 evaluated by breakthrough testing. The characteristic parameters: breakthrough time $t_{5\%}$;
184 breakthrough volume $V_{5\%}$; and dynamic sorption capacity W_d and equilibrium sorption capacity
185 W_{eq} were calculated from the analyses of breakthrough curves (see Section 3 of the Supporting
186 information for more details).

187 Breakthrough experiments were performed with concentrations of 162 mg/STP m³ (32 ppmV)
188 of DMMP in dry N₂. For the remainder of this work, all the volumetric units refer to STP
189 conditions. In order to achieve a reliable and stable DMMP/N₂ stream, 10 cm³/min of dry N₂ was
190 circulated through a calibrated permeation tube of DMMP (VALCO, permeation rate of 1629.96
191 ng/min \pm 0.71% at 100 °C) and fed directly to the μ -preconcentrator. The μ -devices were
192 connected upstream to the DMMP atmosphere generator and downstream to a GCMS (Shimadzu
193 GCMS-QP2010) through fused silica capillaries ($\varnothing_{\text{capillary}} = 320 \mu\text{m}$) and 1/8" Teflon pipes. The
194 eluted gas concentration was sent to analyze each 60 s through a 500 μL sampling loop and the
195 characteristic DMMP fingerprint (u.m.a: 79, 94, 109 and 124) was quantified. The μ -
196 preconcentrator was reconditioned overnight at 473 K under 10 cm³/min dry N₂ stream.

197 The preconcentration performance of the μ -device is evaluated from its preconcentration
198 coefficient, denoted as K ²⁴. This parameter mainly depends on the adsorbent type and loading,
199 the trapping efficiency, the number and nature of competing vapors in the sample and the sample
200 volume. According to IUPAC guidelines²⁵, this value is defined as the ratio of the air sample
201 collected volume to the volume in which that same mass is released according to the
202 quantification at the point of detection, assuming no transfer mass losses take place.
203 Accordingly, the K estimation is carried out under experimental conditions that guarantee the

204 absence of target molecules in the outlet stream, *i.e.* no breakthrough conditions.
205 Preconcentration experiments were performed with atmospheres of 2.64 mg/m³ (520 ppbV) of
206 DMMP in dry N₂. As previously, atmospheres were generated by circulating 10 cm³/min of dry
207 N₂ through a calibrated permeation tube of DMMP (VALCO, permeation rate of 148.41 ng/min
208 ± 3.07 at 90 °C) and fed to the μ-preconcentrator. The atmosphere was sampled for 10, 30 and 60
209 min at 298 K, after which the μ-device was firstly swept with 3 cm³/min of the GCMS carrier
210 gas (He) for 5 min at room temperature and then at 473 K. The desorbed pulse of concentrated
211 DMMP was injected to GCMS. Further information on set-up configurations used on
212 breakthrough and preconcentration experiments can be found in Section 3 and Section 4 of the
213 Supporting Information.

214 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

215 **Potentiometric working mode for Cu-BTC electrosynthesis: effect of current density**

216 Current density J plays a crucial role in electrosynthesis. This parameter governs the Cu
217 electrode oxidation rate; and consequently, the concentration of Cu²⁺ ions in the electrolyte
218 solution available for Cu-BTC crystallization. A pristine Cu-Cr/Au substrate as well as a
219 processed one were analyzed by energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) to illustrate the
220 reactive Cu processes. As shown in Figure 2.a, the atomic analysis reveals an homogenous
221 distribution of Cu, Au and Cr layers, with a signal intensity proportional to layer thickness and
222 beam penetration (theoretical electron penetration of incident beam 427 nm for an accelerating
223 voltage of 10 kV on the Cu–Au/Cr substrate was calculated according to published work²⁶).
224 After electrochemical synthesis, the mapping of C signal (mainly attributed to the organic linker)
225 correlates well with the distribution of Cu-BTC crystals over the substrate where the most
226 intense Cu signals are also recorded (Figure 2.b). In contrast, the Cu signal is clearly attenuated

227 on the naked surface in accordance to the lesser Cu thickness; whereas the Au and Cr signals are
228 proportionally increased.

229
230 **Figure 2.** SEM-EDS results and visual inspection on Cu–Cr/Au substrates. a) pristine Cu–Cr/Au
231 substrate: on the left side a SEM micrograph of the analyzed area; on the right, from top to
232 bottom and left to right, the registered signals of C (white), Cu (green), Au (yellow) and Cr
233 (blue) on the centered area of the SEM micrograph. b) sample #2_20 ($J_{\text{synthesis}}=17.3 \text{ mA/cm}^2$, 20
234 cycles): the images are displayed as previously. c) Composed image of the back side of Cu–
235 Cr/Au substrates before and after electro-synthesis under optimized conditions: $J_{\text{synthesis}} = 17.3$
236 mA/cm^2 , 15 cycles.

237 At current densities above 1.5 mA/cm^2 , Cu-BTC crystallization begins to occur preferentially
238 at the borders of the metal electrode where the Gibbs free energy of the nucleation process is
239 decreased due to the presence of more grain boundary defects. By increasing the number of
240 cycles, the population of discrete Cu-BTC crystals grows rapidly all along the metal substrate,
241 but without forming a continuous and homogenous layer (Figure 3.a). At the highest current
242 density tested ($J_{\text{synthesis}} = 28.8 \text{ mA/cm}^2$), Cu-BTC layer formation is equally unsuccessful (Figure

243 3.c). This observation is attributed to the instability of the glass Cr/Au-Cu interface, more
244 pronounced at higher overpotentials (above 9 V) due to the electro-migration of Cr atoms into
245 the Au films (Figure 2.c).²⁷ In addition, the inter-diffusion of Cr into Au layers is temperature
246 dependent, i.e. solubility of Cr in Au at 323 K increases up to 5 atom %.²⁸ This mechanism
247 would provoke an unsteady current density distribution profile over the working Cu electrode
248 immersed in the electrolyte solution at 313 K resulting in a heterogeneous coverage of the
249 substrate. Among the tested conditions, the most homogeneous Cu-BTC coatings are attained at
250 $J_{synthesis} = 17.3 \text{ mA/cm}^2$ in a range of synthesis cycles from 10 to 20 (Figure 3.b). The
251 characteristic turquoise color of Cu-BTC is clearly noticed over the whole electrode surface. This
252 observation correlates well with the SEM analysis performed at random spots of the surface.

253
254 **Figure 3.** Electrochemical synthesis of Cu-BTC on Cu-Cr/Au substrates: a) sample #1_12:

255 $J_{\text{synthesis}}=1.6 \text{ mA/cm}^2$. b) #2_15: $J_{\text{synthesis}}=17.3 \text{ mA/cm}^2$. c) #3_12: $J_{\text{synthesis}} = 28.8 \text{ mA/cm}^2$.

256 **Cu-BTC electrosynthesis on Cu-Ti substrates**

257 Cu-BTC electrosynthesis on Cu-Ti substrates was also investigated in order to overcome the
 258 instability issues of the glass-Cu interface due to chromium electromigration. As reported by Hsu
 259 *et al.*²⁹, titanium atoms do not tend to diffuse into Cu films and a well-defined Ti layer; and a
 260 stable Ti-Cu interface is commonly obtained. Unlike Cu-Cr/Au substrates, the Cu thickness in
 261 Cu-Ti substrates was increased up to 500 nm to ensure that Cu-BTC crystal growth is not
 262 eventually hindered by the concentration of Cu ions in the electrolyte solution. Likewise, the
 263 electrosynthesis parameters were slightly modified in accordance to the variations in the energy

264 required to overcome the electric resistance of the equivalent circuit, i.e. metal substrate –
265 reaction media – counter-electrode.

266 Figure 4 summarizes the characterization of sample #4_15, i.e. $J_{\text{synthesis}} = 8.6 \text{ mA/cm}^2$, N_{cycles}
267 =15. The visual inspection (Figure 4.a) clearly confirms the homogeneity of the continuous Cu-
268 BTC film $4.7 \pm 1.1 \mu\text{m}$ thick, as measured by profilometry, equivalent to $113 \pm 26 \mu\text{g}$ assuming
269 0.35 g/cm^3 as MOF density. The spatial EDS mappings of Cu and C atoms (Figure 4.b) clearly
270 overlap each other, whereas the Ti signal remains nearly constant, only slightly shielded where
271 agglomerated octahedral Cu-BTC crystals are encountered on the electrode surface. The
272 crystallinity of the supported Cu-BTC film was evaluated by XRD analysis. In Figure 4.c the
273 main characteristic Bragg reflections at small 2θ angles for HKUST-1 ($2\theta = 5.8^\circ, 6.7^\circ, 9.5^\circ,$
274 11.6° ; corresponding to (111), (200), (220) and (222) crystallographic planes) are observed.¹⁴
275 Unlike the PXRD of commercial Cu-BTC, a preferential crystallographic orientation along the
276 [111] direction is observed for the electrosynthesized Cu-BTC film. In addition, the coexistence
277 of Cu_2O impurities, already present in the pristine Cu-Ti substrate (diffraction peaks at 38.3° and
278 43.5° ³⁰), is clearly noticed as commonly found in Cu-BTC synthesis.³¹

279 Although the XPS measurements give only a semiquantitative elemental composition, the
280 presence of C, O, Cu in the Cu-BTC coating was confirmed. The Cu 2p_{3/2} and Cu 2p_{1/2} lines,
281 found at the binding energies of 934.7 and 954.6eV are ascribed to the binding energy of Cu
282 2p_{3/2} and Cu 2p_{1/2}, respectively, which are presented on Cu-BTC films.³² The peaks of Cu
283 2p_{3/2} and Cu 2p_{1/2} are also de-convoluted into two components (see Figure 4.d). Thus, the
284 fittings of Cu 2p_{3/2} lead to binding energies of 932.6 and 934.7 eV, which correspond to surface
285 Cu^+/Cu^0 and Cu^{2+} species, respectively. A quantitative analysis on the Cu 2p_{3/2} XPS spectra

286 gives rise to the surface $\text{Cu}^{2+}/\text{Cu}^{+}/0$ M ratio of 1.017. Similarly, the Cu 2p_{1/2} peak is de-
287 convoluted in two components at 952.7 and 954.5 eV.

288 In addition, there are three shake up satellite peaks, which are typical Cu^{2+} in cupric
289 compounds. These satellite peaks, on the high binding energy side of the core level Cu 2p XPS
290 data at 939.8, 944.1 and 963.1 eV, originate from multiple excitations in copper oxides and they
291 are known to be characteristics of CuO phase.³³ Therefore, the presence of the intense shake-up
292 satellite structures observed in the Cu 2p XPS spectra of D3 sample, accounting for circa 35% of
293 total copper content on the surface, was an indication of the simultaneous formation of Cu-BTC
294 and CuO phases, on the surface of the electrosynthesized films.

295 The starting Cu/Ti electrode was also examined. Peaks at 932.8 eV (Cu 2p_{3/2}) and 952 eV (Cu
296 2p_{1/2}) and the absence of satellites shake-up lines characteristic of Cu^{2+} give clear evidence that
297 Cu is present in the +1 oxidation state, in agreement with the XRD spectra shown in Figure 4.c.

298

299 **Figure 4.** Electrochemical synthesis of Cu-BTC on Cu-Ti substrates: sample #4 ($J_{\text{synthesis}} = 8.6$
 300 mA/cm^2 , $N_{\text{cycles}} = 15$). a) Optical image, below SEM micrograph of a representative area of the
 301 coating. b) SEM-EDS results on the clamping region highlighted in a), showing the overlapping
 302 of Cu (green) and C (white) signals. c) XRDs of the Cu-BTC film (blue), pristine Cu-Ti substrate
 303 (red) and commercial Cu-BTC powder (black). Crystallographic patterns from.¹⁴ d) Core level
 304 Cu₂p XPS spectra of the Cu-BTC film (blue) and pristine Cu-Ti substrate (red).

305 Figure 5 shows the chronopotentiometric measurements with time on stream. This analysis is
 306 revealed as a reliable characterization tool for the assessment on the heterogeneous Cu-BTC
 307 crystallization process. A smooth increase of the electric potential difference across the working
 308 and counter electrodes would be expected with electro synthesis time and number of cycles.
 309 Assuming constant the electrolyte's and the counter-electrode's resistivity, this slight effect
 310 would be explained by the evolving working electrode, which becomes more insulator with
 311 synthesis time due to the lesser conductivity of Cu-BTC films ($\sigma_{\text{Cu-BTC}} < 3 \times 10^{-9} \text{ S/m}$ vs. $\sigma_{\text{Cu}} =$
 312 $5.96 \times 10^7 \text{ S/m}$).³⁴ Overlapped voltage signals are registered for #4_15 (1) and #4_15 (2)
 313 samples, respectively; both prepared under identical conditions ($J_{\text{synthesis}} = 8.6 \text{ mA/cm}^2$, $N_{\text{cycles}} =$
 314 15). More specifically, the applied overpotential slightly increases from 4.1 V for the 1st cycle to
 315 4.7 V in the 15th cycle in agreement with the controlled formation of homogeneous Cu-BTC
 316 films. Accordingly, these conditions have been selected for the fabrication of the functional
 317 microdevices for sampling and preconcentration of nerve agents (NAs) diluted in gaseous
 318 streams.

319

320 **Figure 5.** Chronopotentiometric analyses along the Cu-BTC electrosynthesis over Cu-Ti
321 substrates: #4_15 (1) in blue, #4_15 (2) in yellow, #5_7 (1) in purple, #5_7 (2) in red, #5_15(1)
322 in green and #5_15(2) in orange.

323 On the contrary, on samples #5_7 and #5_15, both at $J_{\text{synthesis}} = 17.4 \text{ mA/cm}^2$; the overpotential
324 evolution rate with time on stream is substantially higher from the 4th cycle and particularly
325 noticeable on 9th cycle. We attribute this observation to the detachment of the Cu-BTC layer
326 from the working electrode due to the exhaust of the Cu layer and the reduction of the
327 electroactive surface area.

328 **Water and DMMP adsorption properties of Cu-BTC powder**

329 Figure 6.a shows the characteristic Type I Ar isotherm at 87.3 K for commercial Cu-BTC. The
330 BET surface area is $1812 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ (correlation coefficient of 0.9999). Micropore size distribution
331 has been modeled using nonlocal density functional theory (NLDFT) and considering cylinder
332 shape pore. The pore network of Cu-BTC has a simple cubic symmetry. It consists on a 3
333 dimensional channel system with main pores of ca. 9 \AA and tetrahedral side pockets of ca. 5 \AA .³⁵
334 Such pore size distribution is illustrated in Figure 6.b with a total pore volume of $0.81 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$.

335 Cu-BTC is extremely sensitive to water content due to the very strong interaction between
336 open Cu(II) sites and water molecules.²⁷ TGA of the as received Cu-BTC is shown in Figure 6.c.
337 The first weight-loss up to 373 K accounts for $1216 \text{ mg/g}_{\text{CuO}}$ and it is mainly associated with
338 water content due to the relatively hydrophilic large pores. On the contrary, the water content of
339 activated samples is notably reduced, i.e. $150\text{-}175 \text{ mg/g}_{\text{CuO}}$ (Table 2). This observation highlights
340 the importance of the thermal activation to empty the framework efficiently.³⁶ The sample does
341 not show any significance weight change up to circa 523 K, onset temperature for the organic
342 linker degradation.

343
 344 Figure 6. Textural characterization and TGA of commercial Cu-BTC (Basolite C300) a) Ar
 345 adsorption isotherm (blue) and NLDFT model fitted curve (red). Insert: detail of low-pressure
 346 region ($0.0 < P/P_0 < 0.1$) of Ar adsorption isotherm (blue) and NLDFT fitted curve in
 347 logarithmic scale. b) Pore volume distribution (blue) and cumulative pore volume (red)
 348 according to NLDFT model assuming cylinder shape pore. (c) TGA (continuous line) and DTA
 349 (discontinuous line) of as received sample. d) Thermal stability of as received sample at 523 K in
 350 N₂ atmosphere for 36 h. Insert: detail for the first 5 h exposure time.

351 An aliquot of as received Cu-BTC sample was exposed to the fabrication process conditions to
 352 assess the framework thermal stability during the anodic bonding, i.e. 523 K for 36 h (see Figure

353 6.d). A similar water weight loss is registered during the first heating ramp up to 523 K. During
 354 the next 5 h at 523 K, no appreciable weight loss is recorded. Afterwards, the slope increases
 355 gradually with time on stream. After 36 h exposure at 523 K, the weight loss due to the partial
 356 degradation of the organic linker accounts for 11 %. Accordingly, the anodic bonding conditions,
 357 523 K @ 1 kV, were kept for 5 h to preserve the Cu-BTC framework.

358 **Table 2.** DMMP adsorption on Cu-BTC at 293 K estimated by TGA

	<i>Activated Cu-BTC</i>		<i>As received Cu-BTC</i>	
	$\Delta m < 373 K$ (mg/gCuO)	$\Delta m > 373 K$ (mg/gCuO)	$\Delta m < 373 K$ (mg/gCuO)	$\Delta m > 373 K$ (mg/gCuO)
Control*	150	–	1216	–
DMMP (3748 mg/m ³)	175	771	–	–
DMMP + Water (3748 mg/m ³ + 7362 mg/m ³)	238	297	323	267

359 *analyses on raw samples, without being exposed to DMMP or DMMP + water atmospheres

360
 361 Table 2 comparatively shows the water and DMMP uptake values of activated Cu-BTC
 362 samples for single DMMP (*DMMP@3748 mg/m³*) and binary DMMP + water mixture
 363 (*DMMP@3748 mg/m³ + water@7362 mg/m³*) in N₂, respectively. The first weight-loss up to
 364 373 K is attributed to water desorption, whereas those shown at temperatures above 373 K are
 365 due to DMMP release. According to tabulated data, DMMP uptake is shown to be dependent on
 366 the water content of the gas stream with a maximum DMMP sorption capacity of 771 mg/g_{CuO} at
 367 dry conditions. For single DMMP adsorption on activated samples, the differential thermogram
 368 reveals the existence of three different sorption sites with different interaction energies (Figure

369 7.a). It is also found that most of the weight loss to DMMP desorption occurs at 433 K, Δm_{DMMP}
 370 = 473.0 mg/g_{CuO}, vs. 112 mg/g_{CuO} @ 500 K and 186 mg/g_{CuO} @ 543 K. For the binary mixture
 371 (Figure 7.b), the DMMP uptake of activated sample is notably reduced to less than half, i.e. 297
 372 mg/g_{CuO}; and the triple peak that was seen before, no longer appears. This value is only slightly
 373 superior to the quantified for co-adsorbed water vapor, i.e. 238 mg/g_{CuO}.

374 a) DTA of activated Cu-BTC before (black) and after exposure to 3748 mg/m³ DMMP
 375 in dry conditions (blue). Slashed blue lines depict de-convoluted peaks of exposed Cu-BTC. b)
 376 DTA of activated Cu-BTC (red) and as received Cu-BTC (green) after co-exposure to DMMP
 377 (3748 mg/m³) and water (7362 mg/m³). Slashed red and green lines depict de-convoluted peaks
 378 of activated Cu-BTC (red) and as received Cu-BTC (green).
 379

380 In “as received” Cu-BTC, the starting amount of pre-adsorbed water vapors (1216 mg/g_{CuO})
 381 has almost no influence on the final DMMP uptake in comparison with the activated sample: 267
 382 mg/g_{CuO} versus 297 mg/g_{CuO}. In both samples, a broad peak centered at 473 K associated to
 383 DMMP desorption is observed in the differential thermograms. In other words, the binding
 384 energy of DMMP- uncoordinated Cu(II) sites is lower in presence of co-adsorbed water vapor.

385 We attribute this effect to the formation of a DMMP-complex on the Cu(II) paddlewheels, where
386 the strong interaction of non-bridging phosphoryl oxygen atom in DMNP with uncoordinated
387 Cu(II) sites is attenuated due to proximity of water Cu(II) coordinated sites. Thus, the formation
388 of weaker hydrogen bonds between the hydroxyl groups present on the water Cu(II) coordinated
389 sites C and the P=O function of DMMP is softening the energy barrier for DMMP desorption. In
390 addition, the facilitated diffusion of desorbed DMMP molecules from the hydrated pores of Cu-
391 BTC is positively contributing due to the hydrophilic character of the surrogate.³⁷

392 Moreover, water adsorption of as received Cu-BTC sample is reduced to almost a quarter in
393 presence of DMMP, i.e. 1216 mg/g_{CuO} in non-competitive water adsorption scenario vs. 323
394 mg/g_{CuO} for the binary mixture. Thus, the presence of DMMP in a competitive sorption scenario
395 is able to dehydrate the Cu-BTC sample and to allocate on active sites previously occupied by
396 water molecules.

397 The role of water inclusion in the physicochemical interactions for DMMP sorption within the
398 porous structure of Cu-BTC has been computationally studied to corroborate our hypothesis.
399 Low energy adsorption on surface sites of DMMP and water molecules on periodic Cu-BTC slab
400 built on different crystal orientations have been identified through Monte Carlo (MC)
401 simulations. In order to find minimal energy of the system, the temperature was modified
402 externally to simulate the annealing of the system from 100 K to 10⁵ K for 20 cycles with 20000
403 of steps per cycle. The molecular interactions have been simulated by using UFF force field and
404 Ewald method as summation method. A similar study was performed on copper/copper oxides to
405 quantify the effect of the electrode and crystalline impurities.

406 Figure 8 shows the adsorption energies for DMMP in absence of co-adsorbed water vapor.
407 Crystal orientation of the simulated Cu-BTC slab plays an important role in DMMP surface

408 adsorption. Morphologies of the structures are also investigated (see Section 5 of Supporting
409 Information). The (110), (101), (011) and (111) orientations for Cu-BTC slabs show similar
410 appearance: oval-shape holes (13.2 Å x 18.6 Å). The (010) and (001) orientations present a
411 cross-shape trench of 6.5 Å, and the intersection of these trenches provides holes of 16.2 Å in
412 diameter. The (110), (101), (011) and preferential (111) crystallographic planes exhibit similar
413 adsorption energies, ca. -55 kcal/mol. On the contrary, the (010) and (001) orientations possess
414 two energy distribution probabilities centered at -51 kcal/mol and -73 kcal/mol, respectively.
415 Additionally, the average of adsorption energy for DMMP molecules adsorbed inside the Cu-
416 BTC micropores is lower than -30 kcal/mol. Such differences in the binding energies are
417 supporting the differential DMMP desorption profile shown in Figure 7.a. Thus, the broad peak
418 centered at 433 K would be attributed to the release of DMMP molecules from the Cu-BTC
419 micropores. The release of DMMP adsorbed on the surface seems to occur at higher temperature
420 due to strength of the interactions. The distribution of DMMP molecules on the available
421 sorption sites would explain the three desorption bands observed in the differential thermograms.

422
 423 **Figure 8.** Montecarlo simulations of DMMP interactions over Cu-BTC and Cu₂O/CuO surfaces
 424 without and with co-adsorbed water vapor molecules.

425 Similarly, Figure 8 illustrates how the presence of co-adsorbed water vapor shifts the DMMP
 426 energy distribution probability to lower and more dispersed values. These simulations suggest
 427 that DMMP interactions with Cu-BTC surface become weaker in presence of co-adsorbed water
 428 vapor, supporting our hypothesis on the hydrogen bonding type interactions between the
 429 phosphoryl oxygen atom in DMMP and the hydroxyl groups present on the water Cu(II)
 430 coordinated sites.

431
 432 **Figure 9.** Simulated adsorption isotherms of DMMP, water and sarin gas at 298 K on Cu-BTC
 433 and Cu₂O/CuO surfaces and energy distribution probability for DMMP adsorbed inside the
 434 micropores for single and binary mixtures. The star-type symbols correspond to the experimental
 435 adsorption points shown in Table 2.

436 Figure 9 presents the calculated adsorption isotherms of DMMP, water and sarin gas on Cu-
 437 BTC microporosity at 298 K and the energy distribution probability for DMMP adsorbed inside
 438 pores in presence and absence of water. The discrete experimental points, shown in Table 2, are
 439 also included for comparison purposes. As it can be observed, the calculated values for Cu-BTC
 440 are superior to those experimentally obtained due to the presence of copper oxide impurities for

441 which the sorption properties are notably diminished due to their less surface area. For the
442 calculations 30000 steps and 1000000 production steps have been set on MC parameters. This
443 distribution correlates in same way than observed on case of surface adsorption. In general, the
444 adsorbate uptake values for single components are higher than those calculated for binary
445 mixtures (see Section 5 of Supporting Information). Thus, 73% of reduction for water uptake in
446 DMMP presence is recorded, a very similar value than obtained experimentally (70%). However,
447 DMMP shows a 20% of theoretically decay while experimentally shows a 61%. Our explanation
448 resides in the strong interactions of DMMP with the external surface which are underestimated in
449 the calculated isotherms, where only the molecules inside the micropores contribute to the
450 theoretical approximation. Furthermore, the predicted values for Sarin gas are rather similar to
451 those of DMMP analogue, supporting the suitability of Cu-BTC for Sarin gas detection.

452 **Performance of functional Cu-BTC μ -preconcentrators**

453 Breakthrough testing was performed on Cu-BTC functionalized μ -devices, denoted as
454 uPC_Cu-BTC, and also on analogues without MOF coating, denoted as uPC_Cu, for reference
455 purposes. In addition, a blank experiment with a sealed microdevice without micropatterned Cu
456 electrode (uPC_0) was carried out for baseline subtraction. The durability of the Cu-BTC
457 functionalized μ -devices were confirmed by assessment of the sorption properties upon exposure
458 to several sorption-desorption cycles of DMMP (see Section 6 of Supporting Information for
459 more details).

460 The breakthrough curves shown in Figure 10.a indicate that both uPC_Cu and uPC_Cu-BTC
461 material present close DMMP breakthrough time (3.2 min and 3.8 min respectively, thus 32 cm³
462 and 38 cm³ breakthrough volume at 162 mg/m³). However, dynamic adsorption capacity is
463 higher in uPC_Cu-BTC than in uPC_Cu: 122.4 mg/g vs 41.7 mg/g. In fact, the adsorption rate –

464 which can be inferred by the slope of the breakthrough curve – is similar in both microdevices up
465 to values of 0.5 C_x/C_0 . The estimated adsorbate-adsorbent interaction energy on CuO and Cu₂O
466 surfaces is -58 and -37 kcal/mol, respectively, as depicted in Figure 8. For the later one, the value
467 is lower than the analogue for any Cu-BTC surface but high enough to explain the experimental
468 behaviour. This adsorption occurs thanks to the formation of hydrogen bonds between the
469 hydroxyl groups present on the surface of CuO/Cu₂O concomitant phases dispersed over the Cu-
470 BTC film and the P=O function of DMMP.³⁸ Above all, this effect is hindered by the low surface
471 area of the copper oxides impurities. The simulated adsorption isotherms of DMMP on CuO and
472 Cu₂O structures (Figure 9) show an equilibrium value of almost zero indicating the adsorption of
473 DMMP over these oxides is only due to external surface interactions. From C_x/C_0 higher than
474 0.5, the adsorption rate notably decays on the Cu-BTC functionalized microdevices. Our
475 explanation relies on the saturation of the DMMP adsorption sites distributed on the external
476 surface. Thus, DMMP molecules, strongly adsorbed on the surface of the Cu₂O/Cu crystalline
477 impurities and those on the external surface of Cu-BTC crystals, start to diffuse inside the
478 microporous structure. In this adsorption regime, intra-crystalline diffusional limitations become
479 controlling although the adsorbate-adsorbent interactions within the micropores are less
480 energetic. Whereas uPC_Cu becomes saturated after sampling 772 cm³ of DMMP/N₂, the higher
481 surface area of the Cu-BTC coating increases that volume up to 1541 cm³. Overall, the
482 equilibrium adsorption capacity for DMMP is 691 mg/g for uPC_Cu-BTC @ 162 mg/m³. This
483 DMMP uptake clearly overpasses standard adsorption materials such as active carbons (30.4
484 mg/g @ 230 mg/m³)³⁹ or Tenax TA (39 mg/g @ 500 mg/m³)⁴⁰; as well as certain theoretical
485 values calculated for MOFs (e.g. MIP-177 @ 245 mg/g, UiO-66 @ 403 mg/g)⁴¹.

486 a) b)

487 **Figure 10.** Performance of functional Cu-BTC μ -preconcentrators. a) Breakthrough testing for
 488 microdevices exposed to 162 mg/m^3 (32 ppmV) of DMMP $10 \text{ cm}^3/\text{min}$ dry N_2 : without Cu
 489 electrode (black), without (red) and with Cu-BTC coating (blue). Insert: detail of the
 490 breakthrough curve. b) Preconcentration experiments with uPC_Cu-BTC for 2.64 mg/m^3 (520
 491 ppbV) of DMMP.

492 Finally, the preconcentration performance of the functional Cu-BTC microdevices is
 493 evaluated by means of the preconcentration coefficient, denoted as K. Previous dynamic
 494 experiments with the functionalized microdevices helped us to identify the operating window for
 495 a consistent K determination. The evolution of K for a sarin surrogate concentration of 2.64
 496 mg/m^3 (520 ppbV) as a function of the sample volume, varying from 100 cm^3 to 600 cm^3 , is
 497 illustrated in Figure 10.b. Assuming the entire release of the collected DMMP mass by thermal
 498 flushing at 473 K, the desorption volume is given by the carrier gas flow rate that sweeps the
 499 microdevice, i.e. $3 \text{ cm}^3/\text{min}$, and the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the registered
 500 desorption peak (see Section 4 of the Supporting Information for more details). There is a linear
 501 correlation between K and sample volume, i.e., higher values of K are observed at higher sample

502 volume in agreement with published literature.⁴² The maximum K is 171 and corresponds to
503 half-maximum injection peak width of ~1 min after collecting 1584 ng of DMMP ($V_{\text{sample}} =$
504 600 cm^3). Such preconcentration coefficient would require 60 min of sampling at $10 \text{ cm}^3/\text{min}$. It
505 must be emphasized; however, that similar breakthrough volumes and K values are attained at
506 higher sampling rates, i.e. $100 \text{ cm}^3/\text{min}$, for microfluidic cavities $40 \mu\text{m}$ depth at the expense of
507 higher hydraulic losses. Thus, the latter time period may be reduced to 6 min, more suitable for
508 some applications requiring shorter analytical duty cycles. Analogous experiments carried out
509 with μPC_{Cu} device, not shown here, did not succeed due to their dynamic sorption values were
510 almost null at these experimental conditions.

511 Accordingly, quantitative “on field” determination of NAs could be realized by coupling this
512 functional Cu-BTC μ -preconcentrator to downstream Surface Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy
513 (SERS) based sensor with a DMMP detection limit as low as 130 ppbV and 100 s of response
514 time, already developed in our group.^{43,44} Considering the Sarin acute exposure guideline level
515 (AEGL-3) of 64 ppbV for an exposure of 10 min,³ i.e. the persons expose above this
516 concentration for this period could experience life-threatening health effects or death, the
517 combined Cu-BTC μ -preconcentrator + SERS unit would enable the rapid identification of Sarin
518 when present at concentrations below the threshold AEGL3 value.

519 CONCLUSIONS

520 The results presented in this work confirm the integration of homogenous Cu-BTC films on
521 microdevices via electrochemical assisted synthesis. We have identified the adequate synthesis
522 conditions that lead to reproducible MOF coatings of circa $5 \mu\text{m}$ thick: Cu (500 nm). Activated
523 Cu-BTC powder samples exhibit high adsorption capacity towards DMMP, i.e. $771 \text{ mg/g}_{\text{CuO}}$ at
524 293 K and 3748 mg/m^3 , which overpassed other commercial adsorbents. The DMMP uptake of

525 Cu-BTC samples exposed to DMMP+water binary mixtures is equally noteworthy. Despite the
526 high hydrophilicity of this material (1216 mg_{H₂O}/g_{CuO} at 293 K and 7362 mg/m³ of water), the
527 DMMP adsorption capacity remains remarkable even for humid conditions: above 250 mg/g_{CuO}
528 at 293 K and 3718 mg/m³ of DMMP. In fact, the adsorption of DMMP molecules on the less
529 energetic hydrophilic sites seems to be facilitated in presence of co-adsorbed water vapor in
530 agreement with computational studies. These results are supporting the “on field” application of
531 functional Cu-BTC microdevices as reliable μ -preconcentrators for nerve agents.

532 The functional Cu-BTC based μ -preconcentrators exhibit equilibrium DMMP adsorption
533 capacities up to 690 mg/g at 298 K and 162 mg/m³ (32 ppmV), clearly superior to published data
534 on organophosphorous compounds. A preconcentration coefficient of 171 is determined for
535 sample volume of 600 cm³ containing 2.68 mg/m³ (520 ppbV). These promising results pave the
536 way for further development of microsystems comprising micropreconcentrator and SERS based
537 sensors capable of quantitative determination of NAs under field conditions.

538 ASSOCIATED CONTENT

539 Supporting Information

540 The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publication website at DOI:
541 XXXXXXXXXX.

542 Fabrication of μ -preconcentrators (Section 1), experimental set-up for the electrochemical
543 synthesis on Cu modified glass substrates (Section 2), breakthrough testing of functional
544 preconcentrators (Section 3), experimental set-up for preconcentration factor determination
545 (Section 4), morphologies of the structures used for Montecarlo simulations (Section 4).

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Cu-BTC functional microdevices as smart tools for capture and preconcentration of nerve agents

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Section S1. Fabrication of micropreconcentrators

Fabrication process is divided in five different steps: cavity etching, adsorbent incorporation, microdevice sealing, heater element integration and inlet/outlet ports mechanization (Figure S1).

Cavity etching is the first step performed to fabricate the microdevice. It is divided in to two steps: 1) photoresist deposition, 2) etching and 3) photoresist removal. For the simple geometries as well as large features ($>100\ \mu\text{m}$) and deep cavities ($>20\ \mu\text{m}$) studied in this work, wet etching with KOH was used.

Figure S1. Schematic of microdevice fabrication run.

4" diameter, P doped Si wafers ($500 \pm 20\ \mu\text{m}$ thickness, $\langle 100 \rangle$ crystal orientation, 5 - 10 $\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$ resistivity) supplied by Sil'Tronix Silicon Technologies were used in all of our devices. For wet etching, a specific negative-working photoresist ProTEK[®] (Brewer Science) was used. It features a non-degradable character under alkaline etching conditions – which is essential for wet etching. The optical masks were designed using Clewin5[®] software and printed on high grade acetate film by Micro Lithography Services LTD. The standard optical lithography process is depicted in Figure S2.

Figure S2. Standard optical lithography process on Si wafer for cavity definition.

Once the photoresist is deposited, the Si wafer is placed in a custom PEEK holder and immersed vertically in a KOH (40%v) bath at 353 K for a set amount of time. Commonly, etching times of 20 min are used for etching depths of 20 μm .

Figure S3. Optical image of the whole 4" diameter Si wafer ready for dicing and anodic bonding.

For the fabrication of Cu-BTC based micropreconcentrators, the coating “step” for adsorbent deposition required the presence of a metallic thin film. This metallic thin film was not performed on the Si cavity but on the top Borofloat cover by standard lift-off process as schematically described in Figure S4.

Figure S4. Patterning of metal substrate for electroanalysis on a Borofloat substrate by standard lift-off process using the photoresist TI35ESX as sacrificial layer.

Section 2. Experimental set-up for the electrochemical synthesis on Cu modified glass substrates

Figure S5. Experimental set-up for the electrochemical synthesis on Cu modified glass substrates: Schematic view of the electrochemical cell (left); optical image of the Cu modified glass working electrode and counter-electrode assembled on a teflon plate (right).

Section 3. Breakthrough Testing of functional micropreconcentrators

Sorption dynamics of the functional μ -preconcentrators were evaluated by analysis of the monitored breakthrough curve. A typical breakthrough curve, as depicted on Figure S6, follows the evolution in time or volume (of circulated gas) of the eluted analyte concentration downstream of the sorption unit. Mostly, the eluted concentration C_x is normalized by the feeding concentration C_0 , so it ranges from 0 to 1.

Figure S6. Typical breakthrough curve where the normalized concentration is plotted as a function of the volume that has been circulated inside the sorption unit.

For this work, breakthrough point is considered as the moment where $C_x / C_0 = 0.05$, which implies that the adsorbent is becoming saturated and begins to be unable to trap all the analyte molecules carried by the feeding gas. The moment at which breakthrough takes place is denoted as breakthrough time (t_b). Similarly, the volume that has been fed to the bed is defined as breakthrough volume ($V_b = t_b * Q_{feed}$, being Q_{feed} : feed volumetric flow). The ratio of uptake sorbate (target analyte) mass up to breakthrough point (m_b) to the sorbent mass is defined as dynamic sorption capacity (W_d). Analogously, the point where the adsorbent is exhausted is denoted as saturation point; and in this work is assumed it takes places when $C_x / C_0 = 0.95$, this point determines the equilibrium sorption capacity when working in dynamic conditions (W_e). The

maximum mass of sorbate can be calculated by integrated the area above of the breakthrough curve (up to $C_x/C_0 = 0.95$).

Figure S7. Scheme of flow arrangement in the experimental set-up for breakthrough testing: a) adsorbent pre-treatment, b) analyte baseline, c) analyte adsorption and d) analyte desorption.

A conventional breakthrough test comprises the following steps (see Figure S7) depicts the schematics of the set up installed at the University of Zaragoza):

1. *Adsorbent pre-treatment*: before the adsorption experiment, the adsorbent is regenerated thermally by placing the microdevice on a hotplate at 200 °C while inert N_2 sweeps the cavity and degas the sorptive layer. Ideally this step is performed until no undesirable specie was detected.
2. *Analyte baseline*: analyte was fed directly into the detector to obtain the baseline signal that is used for calibration. To avoid contamination on the adsorbent material, dry N_2 is circulated through the microdevice while this step takes place.

3. *Analyte adsorption*: analyte is fed to the microdevice until sorbent saturation, which is assessed by previous calibration ($C_{\text{exit}} = C_0$).
4. *Analyte desorption*: the analyte was desorbed under the same conditions as step 1.

Section 4. Experimental Set-up for Preconcentration Factor Determination

Preconcentration experiments were performed with atmospheres of 2.65 mg/m^3 (520 ppbV) of DMMP in dry N_2 . Although this concentration is 8-fold higher than reported lethal value for sarin gas for exposure times up to 10 min (AEGL-3 = 0.38 mg/m^3 , 64 ppbV), it is fairly reasonable value to accurately characterize the μ -device performance at a reproducible concentration without the need to use additionally dilution streams. The synthetic DMMP/ N_2 mixture was generated by circulating 10 STP cm^3/min of dry N_2 through a calibrated permeation tube of DMMP (VALCO, permeation rate of $148.41 \text{ ng/min} \pm 3.07$ at $90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and fed to the μ -device. The monitoring of the desorption peak was performed with a gas chromatograph coupled with a mass spectrometry detector (GCMS, Shimadzu GCMS QP2010) downstream the μ -device. The characteristic DMMP mass signals were followed ($m/z = 79, 94, 109, 124$) as well as the principal uma signals of the main decomposition products: methanol ($m/z = 31$), dimethyl ether ($m/z = 45$), CO_2 ($m/z = 44$) and formaldehyde ($m/z = 29$).

The μ -device is connected to the GCMS 6-port valve through capillary tubing ($320 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ inner diameter) though high temperature septum glued to the Borofloat side of the device. In order to avoid adsorption of the DMMP in the faces of the septa, an intermediate layer of Kapton has been placed between the Borofloat side and the septum. This approach relies on the rapid thermal desorption of DMMP and the adequate carrier flow rate to push out the bolus in a plug-flow fashion, without the need of a focusing stage. Thus, the experimental protocol is reduced to the sampling of DMMP at room temperature and $10 \text{ cm}^3/\text{min}$ for certain time, the flushing out of the DMMP molecules in gas phase with GCMS carrier for 5 min, after which, the adsorbent is rapidly heated at 523 K , releasing the DMMP and being pushed out to the detector by the GCMS carrier (see Figure S8).

Figure S8. Dynamic preconcentration set-up. a) sampling of the DMMP/N₂ mixture. b) Thermal desorption and concentration of the DMMP adsorbed. Between a) and b) takes place a flushing stage (not depicted in the figure). Green line depicts DMMP/N₂ flow path whereas orange line depicts He flow path.

The preconcentration performance of the μ -device as sampling unit is evaluated from its preconcentration coefficient, denoted as K . According to IUPAC guidelines, this value is defined as the ratio of the gas sample collected volume to the volume in which that same mass is released according to the quantification at the point of detection, assuming no transfer mass losses take place. Accordingly, the K estimation is carried out under experimental conditions that guarantee the absence of target molecules in the outlet stream, *i.e.* no breakthrough conditions. Thus, given a desorption peak (see Figure S9), the preconcentration coefficient K is calculated as follows:

$$K = \frac{V_{\text{sample collected}}}{V_{\text{sample desorbed}}} = \frac{Q_{\text{sampling}} * t_{\text{sampling}}}{Q_{\text{desorption}} * FWHM}$$

where Q_{sampling} is the feeding flow rate, t_{sampling} is the sampling time, $Q_{\text{desorption}}$ is the flow rate at which the released sample is being flushing out and FWHM is the full width at half maximum of the desorption peak registered by the detector.

Figure S9. Graphical representation of a typical desorption peak. On the graph are shown the most important descriptive parameters: peak height I_{\max} , full width at half maximum (FWHM) and the asymmetric factor A_s .

Section 5. Morphologies of the structures used for Montecarlo Simulations

Figure S10. Atomistic representation of Cu_2O and Cu-BTC (HKUST) vacuum slabs with different surface orientations.

Figure S11. Atomistic representation of the energy minimized structures for adsorption of DMMP molecules over Cu-BTC (HKUST) vacuum slabs at different crystal orientations.

Figure S12. Adsorption Sites for water (green color) and DMMP (red color) molecules onto Cu-BTC structure.

Section 6. Durability and Stability of Cu-BTC functional microdevices

The durability and stability of the Cu-BTC functionalized μ -devices were confirmed by assessment of the sorption properties upon exposure to several sorption-desorption cycles of DMMP. The breakthrough curves obtained with a #4_15 type functional device, along 1 month testing and being uninterruptedly exposed to ambient air, are shown below. The data analyses reveal an average value of 67.6 ± 1.5 mg/g and 664.4 ± 47.0 mg/g for dynamic and equilibrium adsorption capacities, respectively. These results confirm the stability of the Cu-BTC sorption capacity, and the reusability of the functional microdevices.

Figure S13. Performance of functional Cu-BTC μ -preconcentrator exposed to sequential adsorption-desorption cycle. Run 1 corresponds to the first breakthrough curve. Run 2 shows the breakthrough curve after 1 month testing, i.e. above 20 sorption/desorption cycles. Experimental conditions: Adsorption 162 mg/m^3 (32 ppmV) of DMMP $10 \text{ STP cm}^3/\text{min}$ dry N_2 ; Desorption 12 h at 473 K $10 \text{ STP cm}^3/\text{min}$ dry N_2 .